

**INNOVATIVE TECH SOLUTIONS FOR MONOLOGUE SPEECH
DEVELOPMENT OF B2 LEVEL ENGLISH LEARNERS**

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Abstract. *The article investigates the potential of technology to improve B2 English monologue abilities among language learners. It suggests that traditional methods may not be effective due to insufficient practice and feedback. Innovative technological solutions, such as interactive apps and peer review resources, can promote language proficiency, self-assurance, and creativity.*

Keywords: *B2 English, monologue, technology, language learning, AI, mobile apps.*

Annotatsiya. *Ushbu maqola B2 darajali ingliz tili o'rganuvchilari o'rtasida monologik nutq ko'nikmalarini oshirish uchun yangi texnologiyalar imkoniyatlarini tahlil qiladi. Ya'ni, amaliy mashq va sharhlar borasida an'anaviy usullar yetarli darajada samarali bo'lmasligi mumkin. Bunda, interfaol ilovalar va boshqa o'rganuvchilar bilan fikr almashish imkonini beruvchi manbaalar sifatida innovatsion texnologik vositalar tilni bilish, o'ziga ishonch va ijodkorlikni rivojlantirishi mumkin.*

Kalit so'zlar: *B2 daraja, ingliz tili, monolog, texnologiya, til o'rganish, AI, mobil ilovlar.*

Introduction

Delivering coherent and compelling monologues is an essential skill for B2 English language learners. While typical classroom activities like role-playing and presentations are useful, they may not always provide the focused practice and personalized feedback needed for considerable growth. Technically, B2-level, upper-intermediate learners can practice individually as their proficiency allows them to learn and practice the language autonomously. So, in recent years, technological innovations have opened up new paths for language acquisition, providing a range of creative tools and platforms to improve monologue development in the target language.

The role of technology

A survey of current studies on language acquisition using technology reveals several intriguing findings. Arifah (2014) asserts that internet use boosts students' motivation. Using films in the classroom encourages students to become enthusiastic about the subject and expand their knowledge. When computers and the internet are utilized in the learning process, learners can acquire knowledge in a meaningful way. Technology aids in the development of higher-order cognitive abilities in students. A

successful blend of multimedia and instructional strategies is critical to grabbing students' interest in learning English.

According to Zhao (2013), one of the most important aspects of learning a language is pronunciation. But it's challenging to give constructive criticism. In conventional teaching environments, feedback and modelling are frequently given by an instructor, who may or may not be skilled at assessing students' pronunciation in the first place. Feedback is typically given by asking students to repeat the pronunciation or by providing an abstract explanation of how the sound should be made. The development of speech recognition technology has made it possible for students to get feedback in more efficient and effective ways. It has been observed that the trend of instructional support has been followed by interactive materials in classrooms. Computer-based communication has been demonstrated to be advantageous for language acquisition (Eaton, 2010). Discussions that are facilitated by computers typically have more equal participation than those that are conducted in person. Class discussions become more collaborative as a result of teachers or a few vocal students not controlling the floor. Zhao (2013) backed up this argument by saying that exposure to and access to interesting, real, and understandable but challenging resources in the target language are crucial for effective language learning.

AI-Powered Language Learning Platforms

The AI-driven systems are able to examine pupils' speech patterns, pinpoint areas in need of development, and offer tailored feedback. AI systems are able to generate personalized lesson plans according to each learner's unique strengths and shortcomings. Early AI research mostly concentrated on grammar, but more recent studies have demonstrated that as computer technology has advanced, AI's capabilities have expanded significantly. The primary focus of research on AI and language teaching and learning has been on tool creation, experimentation, and assessment, as well as attitudes, perspectives, and study reviews. Liu (2009) created a mobile AR learning system using sensors and a handheld AI-related device to help English language learners with their speaking and listening exercises. The findings demonstrated that pupils' speaking and listening abilities in English had improved.

According to Cherner (2023), simulations have been used for decades in the military and medical industries for training reasons where human involvement or feedback is required. Researchers have been using these technologies to help students improve their public speaking abilities. Recently, simulations and artificial intelligence have been combined to create digital settings that mimic real-world

events. Nevertheless, as AI-PPPs are a new technology, not much research has been done on how effective they are. In the great majority of these case studies, one VR (virtual reality) application or simulation was evaluated as an efficient way to help students improve their public speaking abilities in a controlled context, such a lab or classroom. By enhancing presentation quality, AI-powered presentation platforms, or AI-PPPs, are transforming conventional teaching techniques. These services let users practise with AI avatars in low-stakes settings. Users are shown their presentation deck and timed in a designated area. AI provides feedback and improves the presenting experience by analyzing their eye contact, speech habits, and filler language.

Platforms for Language Exchange and Mobile Apps

Mobile applications provide a practical means of honing speaking abilities, including practicing monologues. Real-time communication and feedback can be obtained by establishing connections with other language learners or native speakers. According to Yang (2013), some highly regarded App Store apps should be examined to comprehend the most recent advancements in the field. Using its integrated speech recognition, *SpeakingPal English Tutor* allows students to speak, listen to, and review dialogues. *AutoSpeaking* uses a four-step teaching approach: when a recorded sentence is played, repeat the dialogue; use a shadow to speak while the audio is playing; practise the language by acting out scenarios; and conclude by recapping the words and expressions. Later on, all recordings can be listened to again. *Liulishuo* has added a social component, where students upload their recordings and share their rank scores. *Speaking Training* and *Liulishuo* also use speech recognition technologies to entice users to engage with the device.

According to my own experience with other smartphone apps, *Speaky* and *RealLife* are popular among intermediate-level English language learners. The free language exchange website *Speaky* allows users to meet individuals from all around the world and learn languages from native speakers. *RealLife* is a language-learning program that teaches and communicates in English outside of the classroom.

Conclusion

By adopting technology, educators may empower B2 English students to take their monologue abilities to the next level. They may create innovative and exciting educational environments that promote fluency, confidence, and linguistic creativity by incorporating cutting-edge technology into their teaching methods.

Reference:

1. Arifah, A. (2014). Study on the use of technology in ELT classroom: Teachers' perspective. M.A. Thesis, Department of English and Humanities, BRAC University, Dhaka, Bangladesh.
2. Cherner, Todd & Fegely, Alex & Hou, Chenyu & Halpin, Peter. (2023). AI-Powered Presentation Platforms for Improving Public Speaking Skills: Takeaways and Suggestions for Improvement. *Journal of Interactive Learning Research*. 34. 339-367.
3. Eaton, S. E. (2010). *Global trends in language learning in the twenty-first century*. Calgary, Canada: Onate Press.
4. Liu, T. (2009). A context-aware ubiquitous learning environment for language listening and speaking. *Journal of Computer Assisted Language Learning*, 515-527.
5. Parvin, R. H., & Salam, S. F. (2015). The effectiveness of using technology in English language classrooms in government primary schools in Bangladesh. *FIRE: Forum for International Research in Education*, 2(1), 47 - 59. <http://preserve.lehigh.edu/fire/vol2/iss1/5>
6. Solak, Ekrem. (2024). Revolutionizing Language Learning: How ChatGPT and AI are changing the Way We Learn Languages. *International Journal of Technology in Education*. 7. 353-372. 10.46328/ijte.732.
7. Yang, Bowen & Zhou, Shijun & Ju, Weijie. (2013). Learning English Speaking through Mobile-Based Role-Plays: The Exploration of a Mobile English Language Learning App called Engage. *The EuroCALL Review*. 21. 27. 10.4995/eurocall.2013.9788.
8. Zhao, Y. (2013). Recent developments in technology and language learning: Literature review and meta-analysis. *CALICO Journal*, 21(1), 7-27.